

Adult brachypterous BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* were collected from pots and anesthetized with chloroform. Haemolymph was collected in 0.01 M phosphate buffer by pressing the BPH under a cover glass. Clumped cells and plasma were separated and homogenized in 0.01 M phosphate buffer. The homogenate contained prophenol oxidase.

The effect on prophenol oxidase of insecticides BHC and carbaryl and known activator chymotrypsin (Sigma) was observed. We incubated 100 μ l of

the enzyme source with 100 μ l of the insecticides (1 mg/ml dissolved in 0.01 M phosphate buffer). The reaction mixtures were incubated for 30 min and 100 μ l of 10 mM substrate dihydroxy phenyl alanine (Sigma) was added. Enzyme activity was measured at 480 nm after adding 1.7 ml of 0.01 M phosphate buffer. An appropriate blank and control were maintained. BHC, chymotrypsin (1 mg/ml), and carbaryl were tested separately for activation capacity.

BHC had greater activating capacity

Prophenol oxidase activation by carbaryl, BHC, and chymotrypsin, Coimbatore, India.

Activator	Prophenol oxidase activity (OD/mg protein per 30 min)
Carbaryl	0.186
BHC	0.244
Chymotrypsin	0.337

^a Values were confirmed by 3 different determinations.

than carbaryl, and chymotrypsin more than the insecticides (see table). Thus, a preliminary defense mechanism is set up against the stress caused by insecticide application. \int

Mass rearing *Tyrophagus palmarum*

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Tyrophagus palmarum Oudemans (Acaridae: Astigmata) mite infests rice seedlings and leaf sheaths in the nursery and field. We developed a mass rearing technique to provide enough *T. palmarum* mites for biological studies.

Oatmeal agar (OMA) medium with 4% oatmeal, 2% agar agar, and 2% sucrose was prepared and autoclaved at 15 lb pressure for 30 min. Ten ml of the medium was poured into sterile 5-cm petri plates. Each petri plate was inoculated with *Fusarium moniliforme* and kept at room temperature (26 \pm 3°C). When petri plates were covered with fungus mycelia, two newly emerged female mites were released on the fungus and incubated in darkness at 85 \pm 3% relative humidity and room temperature 26 \pm 6°C. F1 progeny developed after 12 d and adults and juveniles were counted. Two subsequent generations also were counted (see table).

The mite generally reproduces parthenogenetically and produces mostly females. Mite population was highest in the 2d generation and declined thereafter, as more fungus was eaten. The culture can be continued by inoculating freshly prepared fungi in the petri plates.

To select the best growth medium and standardize the rearing technique, we

Juvenile and adult populations^a of *T. palmarum* mite in 3 generations, Cuttack, India.

Generation no.	Eggs (no.)	Larvae (no.)	Nymphs (no.)		Adults (no.)
			Protonymphs	Deutonymphs	
1	36	8	10	24	167
2	153	73	46	96	864
3	28	12 ^b	93 ^b	641 ^b	3

^aAv of 10 replications. ^bInactive forms.

screened 10 culture media: oatmeal agar 2% and 4%, peptone 2% and 4%, malt extract 2% and 4%, potato dextrose agar, nutrient agar, Elliott's agar, and Czapek's Dox agar. Oatmeal agar 4% was the most suitable medium for fungus and mite multiplication. *F. moniliforme* produced higher mite populations than *Curvularia* sp.,

Alternaria padwickii, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

Cultured mites were tested for the ability to infest. When adult mites were released on 10-d-old potted Karuna seedlings, symptoms (yellowing and drying) developed 15 d later and were similar to those that developed under natural conditions. \int

Host plant range of the planthopper *Nisia atrovonosa*

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The planthopper *Nisia atrovonosa* lives on weedy bunds of irrigated transplanted rice in Koronadal, South Cotabato, Mindanao. Its host range is unknown; its pest status is not understood. We studied the growth and longevity of *N. atrovonosa* on different weed species and rice. Growth was measured as the percentage of nymphs that reached adulthood and their growth period.

N. atrovonosa has a limited host

range. It was successfully reared on *Cyperus rotundus* and *C. iria* (see table). More nymphs reached adult stage on *C. rotundus* than on *C. iria*, suggesting that *C. rotundus* may be the planthopper's main host. Development stopped at the first nymphal instar on *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Brachiaria distachya*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Paspalum distichum*, and *Leptochloa chinensis*, and at the second nymphal instar on *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Echinochloa glabrescens*, *Eleusine indica*, and *Oryza sativa*. On *C. compressus* and *C. brevifolius*, it developed to a late nymphal stage but did not reach adulthood.

Results suggest that *N. atrovonosa* is not a rice pest. This was further